

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING DIGITAL COMPETENCE

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada raqamli kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslarini keng va chuqur holatda o'rganib tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot davomida o'quvchilarning va ishtirokchilarning raqamli ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish jarayonida o'qitish metodlari, motivatsiya, tanqidiy fikrlash, mustaqil o'rganish va psixologik xususiyatlarning o'z ichiga olib o'rganildi. Shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning afzalliklari bilan bir qatorda, bu jarayonda yuzaga keladigan muammolar ham tahlil qilindi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, raqamli kompetensiyani samarali rivojlantirish faqat texnologiyalarga bog'liq emas, balki to'g'ri pedagogik yondashuv va o'quvchilarning psixologik tayyorgarligiga ham bog'liq.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli kompetensiya, pedagogika, psixologiya, ta'lim, tanqidiy fikrlash, mustaqil o'rganish

Аннотация. В этой данной статье проводится такие анализы как педагогических и психологических основ развития цифровой компетентности. В ходе исследования были рассмотрены факторы, которые влияют на формирование цифровых навыков у людей, учащихся, включая методы обучения, мотивацию, критическое мышление, самостоятельное обучение и психологические особенности. Наряду с преимуществами использования цифровых технологий были также проанализированы такие проблемы, возникающие в процессе их применения. Результаты показывают что эффективное развитие цифровой компетентности зависит не только от технологий, но и от правильного педагогического подхода и психологической готовности учащихся.

Ключевые слова: цифровая компетентность, педагогика, психология, образование, критическое мышление

Annotation. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the pedagogical and psychological foundations of developing digital competence. During the research, the factors influencing the formation of digital skills in students who are taking exams, including teaching methods, motivation, critical thinking, independent learning, and psychological characteristics. Moreover to these advantages of digital technologies, there are problems encountered in their usage were also analyzed. The results show that the effective development of digital competence depends not only on technology but also on proper pedagogical approaches and students' psychological readiness.

Keywords: digital competence, pedagogy, psychology, education, critical thinking, independent learning

Introduction

In modern society, digital technologies are rapidly increasing, developing and becoming an important part of education. Today, students are expected not only to gain knowledge but also to use digital tools very effectively in the learning process. This creates new requirements for both students and teachers.

Previous times, education was mostly based on traditional methods, where students received information passively, like they were used books, magazines and journals in order to find an appropriate information. However, these days the situation has changed very quickly, and students are more active participants in the learning process. Digital technologies help them to search, analyze, and use information more independently.

Digital competence includes many different skills for example working with information, communicating online, and using digital platforms. However, the process of developing these skills is complex and depends on pedagogical and psychological factors.

The increasing of digital information also creates some difficulties in this field. Students may face problems in choosing reliable sources because most of them provide with fake informations and analyzing large amounts of data. Therefore, it is important to develop not only technical skills but also critical thinking.

Moreover, modern technologies create new opportunities for collaboration. Students can communicate and work together through online platforms like Zoom, Telegram, WhatsApp, Imo, Facebook and more other platforms which makes learning more interactive and interesting. But at the same time, excessive use of digital technologies may have also negative effects, such as dependence on technology or lack of independent thinking. That is why a balanced approach is necessary to balance

The purpose of this article is to analyze the pedagogical and psychological foundations of developing digital competence and to identify effective ways of its development in the educational process.

Theoretical Foundations

The main role of modern technologies in education has been studied and recommended by many people i mean researchers. They were said that that digital competence is not limited to technical skills but also includes cognitive and social abilities.

From the pedagogical point of views, teaching methods play a key and crucial role in the development of digital competence. Interactive and interesting learning process, group working, and project-based methods mostly help students participate actively in the learning environment. From a psychological point of views, motivation is one of the main and important factors.

Students who are interested in learning are most likely to develop digital skills effectively. Their attention, memory, knowledge and cognitive abilities also influence the learning process.

Another important aspect is independent learning. Students should learn how to use digital resources on their own and take responsibility for themselves during learning informations from online courses and platforms.

Researchers also say and highlight the importance of critical thinking. In the digital age, students need to evaluate information and distinguish between reliable and unreliable sources in the platforms.

Main directions of developing digital competence:

1. Searching and analyzing information Digital technologies allow students to access a large amount of informations. However, they need skills to select and analyze this information correctly if they are true or misleading.
2. Use of pedagogical methods
3. Modern teaching methods help integrate digital tools into the learning process and make it more effectively.
4. Psychological readiness

Students' motivation and interest play an important role in learning digital skills.

1. Critical thinking development. Students should be able to evaluate information and make independent conclusions.
2. Use of digital tools. Digital platforms and applications support learning but should be used in a balanced way.
3. Role of the teacher. Teachers guide students and help them develop both digital and thinking skills.

Discussion

The analysis shows that digital competence development is influenced by many factors. Digital technologies provide many opportunities to the students, but their effectiveness depends on how they are used it.

In some cases, students rely too much on technology and do not develop independent thinking. Also, the use of unreliable sources can negatively affect the learning, if the informations were deceitful.

From my point of view, digital tools should support the learning process, but they should not replace human thinking. Students need to develop critical thinking and responsibility by themselves.

Teachers also play an important and crucial role in guiding students and helping them use digital technologies correctly.

Conclusion

The analysis shows that digital competence is an essential part of modern education. It helps students to work with information, communicate, and learn in effective way.

Digital technologies make learning process faster and more accessible. However, their use requires responsibility and fairness.

The development of digital competence depends on both pedagogical and psychological factors. Teachers should create supportive conditions, and students should be active in the learning process.

In conclusion, effective development of digital competence is possible only when technology, pedagogy, and psychology are combined in a balanced way.

References

1. Teaching in a Digital Age Bates, A. W. (2015). Teaching in a digital age. BCcampus.
2. The Data Revolution Kitchin, R. (2014). The data revolution: Big data, open data, data infrastructures and their consequences. SAGE Publications.
3. Education and Technology Selwyn, N. (2016). Education and technology: Key issues and debates. Bloomsbury Academic.
4. Writing in the Digital Age Graham, S. (2018). Writing in the digital age. Cambridge University Press.